

Genre Classification Workflow for the English Short Title Catalogue (ESTC)

Iiro Tiihonen

University of Helsinki

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Abstract

This article introduces an open-box workflow for labelling 94 percent of the English Short Title Catalogue (ESTC) with a unified genre classification scheme, as well as an approach to evaluating the classifications. As the ESTC covers most of the surviving books published in the early modern Anglosphere, our categorisation offers new opportunities for large-scale quantitative research on the early modern book trade. Our evaluation process directly engages with the ambiguity of any genre labelling or annotation schemes of early modern books and highlights problematic boundaries between the categories. We also provide summary statistics about the genre composition of the ESTC, demonstrate how the new data can be used to detect biases in other datasets of early modern books and discuss further possibilities for genre-related computational work with the ESTC.

Keywords: book history, classification, computational history, digital humanities, evaluation process, workflow

Abstrakti

Tämä artikkeli esittelee avoimen työvuoron 94%. ESTC-tietueista kategorisointiin yhtenäisellä luokittelujärjestelmällä sekä lähestymistavan näiden luokittelujen arviointiin. Kategorisointi mahdollistaa uusia laaja-alaisia analyysejä, sillä ESTC kattaa suurimman osan Britti-imperiumissa tai englanniksi varhaismodernina aikana julkaistuista kirjoista. Arviointiprosessimme käsittelee ongelmia, joita varhaismodernien teosten luokitteluun väistämättä liittyy. Lisäksi esittelemme tilastoja ESTC:n genrejakaumasta, osoitamme uuden aineiston höydyn muiden varhaismodernien kirja-aineistojen vinoumien tutkimisessa ja keskustelemme siitä, millaiset laskennalliset lähestymistavat ESTC-teosten genrejen analysointiin voivat olla tulevaisuudessa mahdollisia.

Avainsanat: kirjahistoria, luokittelu, laskennallinen historia, digitaalinen historia, arviointiprosessi, työvuoro

Data availability statement

The ESTC data was obtained by the COMHIS group via agreement from the British Library and University of California Riverside. In accordance with this agreement, the enriched and harmonised ESTC (including the full genre information described here) will be released in a separate data publication in the near future. The code (workflow, its evaluation and analysis) related to this article and the datasets that we can share publicly are available at https://github.com/COMHIS/Genre_classification_workflow_transformations_public_2025. Data not included in the public repository will be provided for replication purposes upon request.

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Authorship statement

Iiro Tiihonen: Conceptualisation (lead), Data curation (equal), Formal analysis, Investigation (equal), Methodology, Software, Visualisation, Writing—original draft (equal), Writing—reviewing & editing (equal). Kira Hinderks: Conceptualisation (supporting), Data curation (equal), Investigation (equal), Writing—original draft (equal), Writing—reviewing & editing (equal). This authorship statement uses the [CRediT NISO standard](#).

This article is part of the ongoing and future-focused efforts of the Helsinki Computational History Group (COMHIS) to harmonise, standardise and enrich the ESTC. This work builds on previous initiatives within the group and lays the groundwork for continued advancements in the field.

1 Introduction

The English Short Title Catalogue (ESTC) is a union catalogue that covers most of the surviving books from the start of the hand press era to the end of the eighteenth century (1454–1800), printed either in the British Isles, Ireland, the colonies of the British Empire or in English anywhere.¹ While some item types (e.g. bookplates; Raven 2018), are missing or unsystematically presented, the ESTC remains the most comprehensive source for conventional books printed in the Anglosphere during the early modern period. The main bulk of the almost 500,000 records represent seventeenth- and especially eighteenth-century books printed in Britain, in English, with the latter century also including tens of thousands of vernacular records from Ireland and North America. Publications in Latin, French or printed on the European continent also number in the several thousands (for a more detailed description of the contents, see for example Lahti et al. 2019). By default, ESTC records can be queried with an interface provided by the British Library. At the time of writing, the interface was inaccessible due to a cyberattack, but a collaborative project (Print and Probability) between researchers from Carnegie Mellon University and University of California San Diego provides access to a fairly up-to-date version of the ESTC data.² Additionally, a beta version of the ESTC, managed jointly by the British Library and ESTC North America, is now available online through the Consortium of European Research Libraries (CERL).³

Since books as material objects have survived exceptionally well,⁴ and the number of copies per edition varies far less than in the modern era,⁵ the data in the ESTC enables a far more comprehensive and interpretable analysis of the objects it represents than most historical datasets. This article presents a workflow for classifying 94 percent of ESTC records with a unified categorisation scheme, describes how the resulting data was evaluated and summarises useful information about the genre distribution of the ESTC and its subsets. We devote significant attention to a systematic close reading of the labels suggested by the workflow and demonstrate how errors and ambiguities can offer insights that are historically and methodologically valuable. We add new

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1. A union catalogue covers the records of multiple libraries.
 2. <https://estc.printprobability.org/>
 3. <https://datb.cerl.org/estc/>
 4. The claimed survival rates (defined as at least one copy of an edition surviving and making it to the ESTC) vary from 55 percent for the period before the English Civil War (Hill 2018) to 70–75 percent for 1640–1700 (Raymond 2003; McKenzie 2002) and 90 percent for the eighteenth century (Suarez 2009). Despite the varying levels of evidence, assumptions and pure guesswork behind these numbers, it is at least safe to say that books as material objects have survived exceptionally well.
 5. There was significant variation in the number of copies printed per edition in the early modern English-speaking world (Jenner 2011; Watt 1990; Simmons 2002), but less so than in the modern era. Roughly 1,000 copies per edition is often presented as a typical number (Raymond 2011; Gants 2002; Hill 2018).

and comprehensive evidence for the argument that the proportion of religious publications declined over time, find a permanent jump in the proportion of political publications during the English Civil War that warrants closer scrutiny, and systematise the analysis of biases in Eighteenth Century Collections Online (ECCO), a significant subset of the ESTC.

Much of the information in the ESTC (publication year, publisher information, physical description of the edition, etc.) has already been extensively processed to a form suitable for data analysis, most notably by the Helsinki Computational History Group (COMHIS) (Lahti et al. 2019). This work on the ESTC is part of the COMHIS effort to harmonise and enrich early modern bibliographic (meta) data collections to make them more useful for historical research. Bibliographic data typically needs preprocessing before rigorous computational analysis is possible (Lahti et al. 2019). Additionally, the work done by COMHIS facilitates easier use of bibliographic data in traditional qualitative history research, such as analyses of text reuse in the early modern period (Rosson et al. 2023).

The workflow described here is a recent addition to this long-term effort by COMHIS. The HPC-HD project—a collaboration between COMHIS and several computer science research groups—has significantly extended the large-scale analysis of language in subsets of the ESTC (most notably ECCO) with state-of-the-art machine learning methods, and created computational approaches for various linguistic phenomena, genre included (Zhang et al. 2022). In addition to this wider context, an article that considered books as commodities that vary by type (Tiihonen, Lahti, and Tolonen 2024) prompted the development of this workflow and employed an earlier version of the outputs.⁶ This article introduces the (revised and improved) workflow for the first time, extends evaluation from a short discussion point in the appendix to a topic in its own right, and provides new information about the generated data. As there is a plan to release the genre data as part of the COMHIS-version of the ESTC in the near future, this article also serves as documentation for the genre variables.

Our conceptualisation of early modern genres is intentionally a very simple one: genre is limited to a single main label per edition (a debatable choice as a unit of text in itself), taken from a pool of very limited choices, and we do not consider many forms of information like visual cues (e.g. images) or complex embedding representations of texts. As we will discuss in the article, many other conceptualisations and corresponding computational paths could and should be explored as well. However, this simplicity also enables effective interpretation of both the process and the results. Moreover, our evaluation of the outputs enables us not only to verify that the labels are largely correct, but

6. For example, almanacks and multi-volume dictionaries would have differed significantly in terms of price, scope of potential buyers and utility.

also to identify potentially fruitful directions for further computational work on early modern genres. Instead of aiming to establish a single permanent and fixed conceptualisation of genre, the workflow presented here is a specific tool for specific applications, which hopefully aids with the development of other classification workflows.

Our workflow has four major advantages compared to preceding efforts to categorise editions in the ESTC. First, it covers virtually the entirety of the ESTC. Second, it is eclectic and leverages the many possible sources of information available, ranging from a large pool of manually annotated documents to established conventions of early modern book titles (e.g. “sermon preached at X”), instead of aiming for a single solution of typically inferior trustworthiness that is intended to cover the entire population to be classified. Third, it is open box. All operations related to classification can be communicated to an audience with little technical expertise. Our eclectic and open-box classification offers an alternative to increasingly employed black-box methods which, although capable of constructing complex decision processes (e.g. about genre), have special challenges in generalising reliably outside of the training data (Kapoor and Narayanan 2023).

Fourth, our evaluation process is tailored to suit the ambiguous nature of many eighteenth-century publications. Instead of having a “gold standard” test set, as is typical in machine learning or statistics, we manually evaluated a large sample of records to assess the relative quality of the label. In addition to clearly right (1) or wrong (0) classifications, we added the category of plausible (0.5), which, as it turns out, covers most of the “errors” in the classified data. Our results highlight that certain genre and topic distinctions are not bugs but features of the early modern publishing landscape: documents at the intersection of politics, religion and law, for example, are inherent parts of the print culture of the era. Instead of forcibly resolving and smoothing historical genre ambiguities, we aim to quantify their size and historically situate their patterns. As analyses of historical bibliographic data are not limited to the ESTC, we hope that our workflow also encourages other researchers working with similar material to consider whether their needs could be served by a simple and transparent workflow for classification and evaluation utilising humanities and resource-specific expertise rather than (or in addition to) the latest computational methods.

This paper is structured as follows: section 2 highlights the limitations of the ESTC’s native genre classification scheme and discusses previous scholarly efforts to mitigate these limitations, for example by creating new classification schemes. This section also examines why the use of unsupervised machine learning models can be problematic for genre classification and stresses the need for detailed process descriptions in articles that introduce new classification

schemes. Section 3 briefly explains the terminology required for understanding the composition and structure of the ESTC and introduces our genre-labelling scheme. Section 4 describes our classification workflow, namely the steps for creating category labels. Section 5 discusses our evaluation of the accuracy of the generated labels. This section also highlights difficulties and pertinent category overlaps, showing that what at first glance appeared to be an error was often a genuine reflection of early modern print culture, where genres were far less distinct compared to the twenty-first century. The sixth section analyses the genre distribution in the entire ESTC, while the concluding section offers suggestions for refinement of our workflow and discusses potential directions for future research on genre classification.

2 The complexity of genre: Previous classification schemes of the ESTC and its subsets

Genre is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon and there is no one correct classification scheme that captures all its nuances in different contexts. The most appropriate scheme is highly dependent on the material and research questions. For historical data, in almost all cases, it is better to use a classification scheme that tries to reflect as closely as possible how historical actors understood genre. However, the genre and subject categories present in early modern union catalogues are often based on library cataloguing schemes that were developed in the nineteenth century, such as the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) and the Library of Congress Classification (LCC). These schemes were created first and foremost to fit the needs of libraries, which differ from the objectives of a scholar wishing to analyse genre distribution patterns in the early modern period. The DDC and LCC reflect nineteenth-century understandings of genre and may impose anachronistic categories on earlier periods or fail to capture genres and subjects that were prevalent in one period but fell out of fashion later. Taking existing classification schemes as is—especially without a systematic evaluation of their biases—can therefore lead to the reproduction of fundamental issues.

Early modern scholars are usually well aware of the limitations of the genre classification schemes native to the ESTC and other union catalogues, but may continue to use them because genres are not their main object of study or because there exists no other option that would be historically more accurate. For instance, one of the earliest quantitative analyses of genre distribution in early modern Britain was based on genre categories taken from the DDC (Feather 1986). The reason for this was that Feather's dataset, the Eighteenth Century British Books (ECBB) short-title union catalogue, used the DDC. A rival catalogue to the ESTC, the ECBB was born out of the Project for Historical Bibliography (PHIBB) at the University of Newcastle and was completed in

1981. Due to its smaller scope and more limited coverage, the ECBB has been dubbed “the poor library’s ESTC” (Barr 1981, 229) and reviewers—some of whom were involved in the then-ongoing development of the ESTC—were only too keen to point out the ECBB’s flaws, including the anachronistic elements present in the DDC (Snyder 1983; Amory 1983). In his quantitative analysis of the ECBB, Feather sought to curb the DDC’s worst excesses by only including high-level subject categories. Despite Feather’s best efforts, some issues remain unresolved: the category of “social sciences,” the second most frequent in Feather’s analysis, is especially problematic. Its individual components are never explained, and the concept, although coined in France in the 1770s (*sciences sociales*), did not become a distinct tradition until the nineteenth century (see for example Baker 1964).

This type of anachronism is not only present in catalogues containing nineteenth-century genre classification schemes; it also affects catalogues whose schemes were developed in the twentieth century. One such example is Eighteenth Century Collections Online (ECCO), the most extensive subset of the ESTC, for which records have been classified by topic. ECCO covers roughly half of the eighteenth-century records of the ESTC and crucially includes digitised and machine-readable versions of the full text of the editions that it covers. Gale, the company that provides access to ECCO, has labelled all records in ECCO with its own classification scheme. Unfortunately, the classification scheme does not suit eighteenth-century records well, since many of the categories do not correspond with historical understandings of genre or fail to capture the granularity of topic differences of the period.⁷ The categories of “social sciences” and “religion and philosophy” are especially problematic in an eighteenth-century context, as they amalgamate very heterogeneous text types.

Scholars have sought to address this problem in multiple ways, with some mitigation strategies more successful than others. Under the assumption that a fully data-driven process can eliminate human biases, unsupervised machine learning methods for classification purposes have become increasingly popular: recent examples include the use of topic modelling on the HathiTrust Digital Library (Almelhem et al. 2023), EEBO (Grajzl and Murrell 2024) and Goldsmiths’-Kress Collection (Tiihonen et al. 2022). The term “topic model” itself is misleading, as it can lead users not familiar with the mathematics of topic models to assume that there is something inherently topic-like in the distributions generated by a topic model. This is not the case, as traditional topic models only generate distributions over units of text, and to our knowledge, other unsupervised methods cannot make sweeping ontological claims either. The general sensitivity of traditional topic models to particulars of

7. ECCO also gives an unbalanced representation of topic distribution in the ESTC (Tolonen, Mäkelä, and Lahti 2022), and we extend the analysis of this issue in the paper.

data preprocessing and the dangers of “eyeballing” interpretations of “topics” (Shadrova 2021; Gillings and Hardie 2023) are highly undesirable qualities when working with historical data. It is hard to see how generating categories with unsupervised methods in general could fully escape these problems.

To better represent early modern conceptions of genre in a way that is most suitable for their own research questions, many scholars have created annotated subsets of the ESTC that focus on specific periods or certain groups of authors (Corns 1986; Gants 2002; Fielding and Rogers 2017; Hill 2018). However, not all publications report the extent to which—or even whether—harmonisation and unification have been performed. Among studies that introduce new classification schemes, a recurring issue is that descriptions of the workflow are sometimes absent or underdeveloped. Rationales for the creation of certain labels and an evaluation of the genre data quality in relation to the existing scholarship are also frequently omitted. For instance, Suarez (2009) proposes an 11-category genre classification scheme for the eighteenth-century part of the ESTC, but does not explain whether this scheme is a modification of the original ESTC subject classification or whether it was developed from scratch. Suarez notes that this genre annotation was performed on a relatively small subset of the ESTC (ca. 24,000 records), but does not systematically assess the coverage of this subset or the precision of his proposed genre categories. Such omissions make it more difficult for readers to understand which research questions can be answered with the help of the newly developed genre classification scheme. At the opposite end of the spectrum are schemes that are highly descriptive but far too reductive to meet the scholarly requirements of historians. Almelhem et al. (2023) map the most common (0.01% of all records using it) subject keywords in the ESTC to just three categories (religion, political economy, science) and use these to study the aggregate genre composition of the ESTC records published in Britain in English. However, as the aim of this study was to test for specific biases in the HathiTrust Digital Library (HTD) data rather than to label the ESTC,⁸ it also demonstrates the increasingly varied and multi-disciplinary interest towards ESTC and its genre composition.

There are two long-standing scholarly traditions of developing and refining genre classification schemes in sync with other bibliographic work on the most important subsets of the ESTC: Early English Books Online (EEBO) at Lancaster University (e.g. Murphy 2019) and ECCO at the University of Helsinki (e.g. Zhang et al. 2022). Both traditions are examples of successfully integrating humanities domain knowledge with sophisticated computational methods. In contrast to unsupervised or Large Language Model-driven approaches, here, the humanities scholar is the prime mover of the process: for example by

8. Appendix figure C.1 in Almelhem (2023) suggests that less than 15% of the ESTC corpus maps to these three categories with the approach they used.

manually annotating large data samples with genre labels, drawing on one's domain knowledge and expertise. By providing a way of classifying genre in the whole ESTC, the workflow introduced in this paper builds on and contributes to this rich tradition.

3 Definitions and taxonomies

3.1 Data vocabulary

This article makes heavy use of terminology designed to distinguish different types of data in the ESTC. For clarity, this section briefly introduces that terminology. The basic unit of the ESTC is a record representing one “printing operation,” that is, a set of copies of a given text printed as part of the same process. In some more complicated situations, this definition and record do not perfectly correspond to each other.⁹ In our vocabulary, records are called editions. The original ESTC records follow the MARC (Machine-Readable Cataloging) format for bibliographic data.¹⁰ The ESTC records have been harmonised, standardised and enriched (Lahti et al. 2019) to a format more suitable for data analysis. Of the raw MARC data fields, the classifications described here rely primarily on the fields that contain the title of an edition (245a and 245b), information about bibliographies that cite a given edition (510a), references to microfilm collections that include a copy of a record (533f), and any fields that contain keywords describing the genre, topic and format of an edition (600, 610, 650, 651, 655). The keywords and full titles were converted to lowercase text in the classification workflow.

In addition to editions, we sometimes refer to works. A work is a grouping of all editions with more or less the same textual content. So, for example, there are several editions of Adam Smith's *The Wealth of Nations* in the ESTC with their distinct edition-level-ID, but they should map to the same work and corresponding work-ID. The ESTC does not hold comprehensive information about works as such, but this information has been algorithmically derived by the COMHIS group based on the title and author information in the ESTC (Ijaz, Roivainen, and Lahti 2019).

Among other information, ESTC editions have a title. Early modern titles were often very long, some even taking the whole first page of the publication. For this reason, they often also have a “short title” (the “ST” in ESTC) for easier

9. For example, multiple issues of a periodical are often stacked under the same record and multi-volume works were sometimes printed in pieces over a long period of time. They are sometimes still grouped together under a single record.

10. <https://www.loc.gov/marc/bibliographic/>

communication. In the classification workflow, we used the longer version of the title, as it provided more information about the topic of an edition.

The ESTC does not have a unified topic or genre classification, but many of the editions have information that is very useful for assigning such a classification. Perhaps most importantly, there are a great number of keywords relating to genre, topic and format that are part of the information characterising records. These keywords like “sermon,” “political controversy” or “anatomy” originate in library cataloguing schemes. As such, they are problematic. There are thousands of unique keywords that are used in the ESTC, yet they are used unsystematically (some records have no keywords and others have many) and their relevance for historical research varies. For example, the keyword “early works to 1800” is very common in the ESTC (at least 12,000 records), but virtually useless for our purposes (it applies to all records). Filtering, mapping and manual curation is required in order to construct historically motivated higher-level categories (e.g. from thousands of varying relevancy to a handful of very relevant ones) suitable for our purposes, which enables the creation of analyses like those displayed in figures 4 and 5. When referring to topic, genre and format keywords in the ESTC, we mean this information.

Additionally, editions in the ESTC often refer to bibliographies or microfilm collections that cite or contain photocopies of the edition. For example, the Goldsmiths’-Kress microfilm collection (Whitten 1978) covers publications relevant for economic history, while *History of English Drama 1660–1900: Volume 6, A Short-title Alphabetical Catalogue of Plays* by Allardyce Nicoll (1959) lists plays. When we refer to microfilm and bibliography collection information in the ESTC, we mean this kind of data.

3.2 Labelling scheme

There are three hierarchical levels in our classification scheme: the supercategory, the main category and the subcategory. Of these, the middle one (**main category**) is the most important. It is a modest modification of the categorisation scheme used in previous articles by the Helsinki Computational History Group (COMHIS) (Zhang et al. 2022; Ryan and Tolonen 2024), and which was also used to classify early modern editions of the ESTC. This categorisation scheme is the result of a thorough investigation of all known books published by Andrew Millar, a prominent eighteenth-century publisher. Rooted in scholarship about early modern book history and designed for the era and location comprising most of the ESTC data (eighteenth-century British Empire), we adopted it and only made minor modifications. The most important difference is that, in our scheme, the physical size of the edition affects its classification (ephemera-entertainment and ephemera-practical only include short editions), and the categories of literature and art have been merged (literature and arts).

In this sense, it is more extensive than most genre-like classification schemes (in comparison to strictly topic-based classifications), as it also considers the material cues (physical size) given by the publication about its category.

The reasoning behind the size-related classifications is that, in some cases, size is an important part of the publication's type. For example, short publications that dealt with scientific matters like astronomy tended to lean more towards immediate practical uses (e.g. almanacs) than longer works with superficially similar contents. As for literature and arts, we concluded that it was too difficult and often not meaningful to distinguish between texts related to performing arts (poetry, plays) and prose; they are often convoluted in eighteenth-century publications (e.g. different kind of miscellanies that contain both), making the distinction very artificial. The subcategories aim to compensate for this merger by specifying the type of publication (e.g. play, poem or novel) with more precision whenever possible.

Table 1: List of the main categories of the classification scheme

Main category	Includes the following publication types
Religion	Bibles, sermons, prayers, theology, religious debates (can also be categorised as politics in some instances), psalms and hymns.
Literature and arts	Periodicals, novels, stories, visual arts, plays, poems, songs, pictures, operas, satires.
Ephemera-entertainment	Chapbooks, broadside poems. Short items (pamphlets) that would otherwise be included in literature and arts, philosophy or history.
Politics	Political pamphlets, societal discussion, news about wars, foreign politics, etc. (note: periodicals are still in literature), commerce, social issues (e.g. poverty).
Law	Legal and administrative documents, legal theory. As a rule of thumb, commentary and debate of legislation are assigned to politics; and description and statement are mapped to law.
Science	Mathematics, natural sciences, agriculture, technology, military organisation and building, logistics (e.g. canals, etc.), natural history, travel literature. Overlaps with literature and arts, notably because of travel literature. Description of facts leans more towards science and satirical, and/or entertaining purposes towards literature.
Education	Manners, upbringing, manuals that instruct on doing something, grammars, primers, dictionaries, conduct of life. Overlaps with topic-related categories (e.g. introduction to mathematics).

Main category	Includes the following publication types
Philosophy	Logic, metaphysics, ethics, political theory, aesthetics, psychology. Overlaps with politics, religion and science in particular. Conceptual/theoretical style of argumentation favours inclusion in this category.
Ephemera-practical	Almanacs, calendars, advertisements, notifications, pamphlet-sized education and science.
History	Historical works, biographies, description of events. Overlaps with literature, as many literary works also take the form of a memoir or “history.” Overlaps with politics, as there is no clear-cut difference between news and recent history.

It is non-exhaustive, as there are always editions that do not fall neatly into any category.

Subcategories provide additional information about the publication in the form of keywords that specify some of its aspects in more detail. There can be multiple subcategories per record and they are separated by semicolons. For example, “poetry” and “commerce” are keywords appearing in the data. In total, 216,000 editions have at least one subcategory. Subcategories are not strictly related to any specific main category, but they often have a strong affiliation with certain main categories. For example, there are 22,000 editions with the subcategory “poem” in the main category “ephemera-entertainment” and 11,000 in the main category “literature and arts.” This makes sense, because by default poems belong to these categories. However, there are also 810 editions with this subcategory in the main category “religion”; this also makes sense in an eighteenth-century context, when religious texts with varying amounts of poetic elements were abundant. Table 2 lists examples of subcategories, with the complete list provided in appendix A.

Table 2: Examples of subcategories and their typical relations to main categories

Subcategory	Typical for main category
Act, bill	Law
Theatre programme, almanac	Ephemera-practical
Petition	Politics
Sermon, prayer book	Religion
Metaphysics, logic	Philosophy
Biography, ancient history	History
Agriculture, medicine	Science
Play, poem	Literature and arts
Broadside poem, chapbook	Ephemera-entertainment

Supercategories aggregate main categories to form even more extensive groups. By using supercategories, one can avoid certain problems caused by systematic convolutions between main categories. For example, if there is no reason to distinguish political pamphleteering from legislative documents, it can be useful to treat them as one category of jurisprudence, which is not affected by the heavy tendency of politics to “bleed” into the category of law at the level of the main category. Supercategories are listed in table 3.

Table 3: Supercategories of the classification scheme

Supercategory	Merges the main categories of
Jurisprudence	Law, politics
Practical	Science, ephemera-practical, education
Leisure	Literature and arts, ephemera-entertainment
Philosophy	Philosophy
History	History
Religion	Religion

4 Classification process

The dataset was created by mapping the ESTC records to main categories and subcategories (described below) in six steps. An edition that acquired a label from one step was not passed to the next one. All steps were looped via the work-ID. This means that if one edition of a work acquired a classification during any of the given steps, this classification was projected to other editions of that work as well. As a result, all editions of the same work should have the same label.

First, all works except periodicals (i.e. works with at least one labelled edition) that were manually annotated in previous COMHIS work with a similar classification scheme (e.g. Ryan and Tolonen 2024; Tiihonen, Lahti, and Tolonen 2024) or as part of this article were given a main category and, if available, subcategories based on the manually annotated data. This resulted in more than 100,000 editions with a main category. Many (30,000) of the manually annotated documents also received a subcategory.

Second, all periodicals detected based on keyword, microfilm and bibliographic data (e.g. in which bibliographies the record is being cited) in the ESTC were labelled as periodicals. That is to say, they were given the main category “literature and arts” and the subcategory “periodical.”

Third, a hand-selected set of ESTC keywords about topic, genre and format of editions were mapped to corresponding main categories and subcategories, and these mappings were used to label works. In exploring potentially useful topic and genre keywords, statistical approaches were used as heuristic tools (see appendix C for details), but all keywords were manually checked. Some keywords were also mapped to a more specific subcategory (e.g. the keyword “medicine” to the subcategory “medicine” in addition to the main category “science”).

Fourth, a similar mapping-to-categories approach was used with n-grams (from monograms to pentagrams) of full ESTC titles. For example, n-grams of the form “sermon preached at” or “proclamations of X” are expressions that tell us the type of a publication (religion and law) very accurately. Here too, statistical tools (see appendix C) were only used as heuristic finding aids; the final approval of an n-gram to the list of n-gram-to-category mappings was a human-made choice. Some n-grams also mapped to more specific subcategories (e.g. “sermon preached at X” to the subcategory “sermon”).

Fifth, ESTC n-grams that were deemed “not good enough but potentially useful” in the fourth step were used. Sixth, keywords that were deemed “not good enough but potentially useful” in the third step were used. For example, the keyword “England” was used at the sixth step, as it often maps to political pamphlets. However, “England” itself can easily relate to non-political topics as well, so the keyword was deemed to carry greater risks than keywords like “sermon” used in the third step, which describe the edition very accurately. That is to say, the sixth step consists of riskier keywords (and the fifth step consists of riskier n-grams) used as a last resort if a more precise describer of the edition is not available.

After the evaluation, main categories were mapped to supercategories that aggregated them further.

In steps three, four, five and six, it was possible for multiple plausible labels to emerge, reflecting the complex reality of early modern genres, which were often far more enmeshed than their modern equivalents. For example, an edition could have both the keywords “sermon” (religion) and “political controversy” (politics). Rather than a category error, this is an accurate reflection of the deliberate topicality of early modern sermons, which were often used to comment on political events. In these instances, the category of an edition was decided based on the prominence (prominence score) of keywords or n-grams related to different main categories (the more prominent the better) and by the number of topics and n-grams of the edition mapping to the category (the more the better). We describe this step in detail in appendix B. Each classified edition of a work then “votes” for the main category of the entire work, with its

vote being equal to the prominence score of the chosen main category. Works classified based on keywords inherit all subcategories to which the keywords of the work map and works classified based on title inherit all subcategories to which the n-grams of the title map.

Figure 1: The workflow to categorise records in the ESTC

This part of the workflow is followed by evaluation of the classifications.

5 Evaluation

5.1 Overview

The quality of the main categories has been evaluated using a mixed methods approach. Two researchers (the authors) went through a random sample of 1,000 records with main categories and 500 without (i.e. the process did not result in a main category for the record). The sample contained information about the size of the document (book, pamphlet or in-between), the part of the process that produced the label, the suggested main category (and, if available, the suggested subcategory), as well as the full title. We decided to use the full title, as eighteenth-century works often contained lengthy subtitles that acted like a table of contents and therefore added important details about the nature of a work. In this period, titles commonly described the contents of a book with genre-related words and expressions that directly map to our classification scheme (e.g. “sermon preached at” or “almanac for the year X”).

Using a metadata sheet with the titles and size information (which is needed for some classifications), the authors were able to classify many of the more straightforward cases much more quickly compared to consulting individual full texts via the ECCO interface, for example. Although the origin of the classification was included in the sheet, this information was not used as the basis for classification choices, and documents that had previously been manually annotated were also scrutinised. Sometimes, the title itself was not sufficient to determine the label. For example, ambiguous and short titles did not allow for inferences about the genre of a text. In these cases, the authors consulted the edition from the ESTC, ECCO and other sources for close reading.

Both annotators scored the labels of the 1,000-record sample using the following scheme: 0 (wrong main category), 0.5 (plausible, but not the best choice) or 1 (best choice or one among equally good choices). A score of 0 was applied when there was no good argument for assigning the particular category to a record. For example, a prayer book classified as science would have received a 0. The classification 0.5 (plausible) was used if there was a good argument for the classification, but the researcher felt that the argument was weaker than for some other category or categories. For example, a pamphlet on religious toleration may have obtained the main category “religion” in the workflow. This would not be a wrong classification per se, but (many would argue) “politics” would be even more appropriate if the pamphlet was more focused on political rights relating to religion rather than religious topics as such. In this case, 0.5 would be an appropriate score. A score of 1 was used if the category of a record was the best one available. A record could receive this score even if there was an equally good (but not better) alternative. For example, a comical poem about commercial policy could be categorised as either “politics” or “literature and arts” with equal plausibility. For records that obtained a score of 0.5 or lower, the researchers also suggested the best possible label. For records with missing labels, the researchers provided their best suggestion. If the metadata, such as size and title, gave no indication of the genre category, both annotators consulted the original text and discussed pertinent issues with each other. These strategies helped to reduce the number of records for which it was not possible to evaluate the assigned label or give an updated label. In the end, a missing evaluation score was a rare phenomenon, occurring only for 0.4 percent of our 1,000-record sample. For the 500-record sample of missing labels, we were unable (i.e. both annotators classified the record as “unknown”) to assign an updated label to 5.2 percent of records.

An important aspect of the evaluation was the two authors’ different degree of involvement in developing the labelling workflow. The six-step workflow was designed and implemented exclusively by the first author, while the initial role of the second author was to provide an independent evaluation of the results. The different relationships (dependent and independent) of the authors to the

workflow is a plausible explanation for the fact that the first author was somewhat more prone to “fully agree” with the annotations provided by the system compared to the second author (see table 4). Having both an “internal” and “external” evaluation perspective in terms of the workflow development led to constructive discussions about the limitations and subjectivities of the workflow.

This manually evaluated data was used to estimate the precision of the main categories (how often they are right) as well as their coverage (how well a main category covers the relevant records). Coverage also takes into account the estimated effect of unclassified and mislabelled editions. In calculating coverage, a classification was considered to be right if the sum score of the two annotators was “good” (at least 1.5/2). A “good” score can be thought of as the label receiving mostly favourable evaluations (at least one score of 1 and one score of 0.5). “Plausible” refers to a sum score that was at least 1 and “best” to a perfect 2/2 sum score. The distribution of genres among editions that did not receive a label from the workflow was calculated by averaging the suggested labels of the two annotators.¹¹

Table 4: Editions from the evaluated sample that obtained a score from both annotators, aggregated by the score they received. N=996

Score (IT)	Score (KH)	N
1	1	807
0.5	0.5	94
0	0	44
1	0.5	41
0.5	0	5
0.5	1	4
1	0	1

The estimates of precision and coverage are summarised in table 5. For all categories, 88–100 percent of the assigned editions are at least plausible. Instances where one annotator gave a score of 0 (wholly incorrect category) and the other a score of 1 (best category) were exceedingly rare. Whenever this kind of scoring did occur, both annotators subsequently consulted the original text and afterwards discussed the reason for their respective scoring. Such discussions often revealed that one of the annotators had consulted the original text before assigning the score, whereas the other had given their score based solely on the title. These measures helped to flag and resolve extreme inconsistencies and acted as additional verification steps for borderline cases. The final distribution of scores is presented in table 4. There is more variation in terms of

11. Averaging was also used to solve instances in which the two annotators suggested a different main category for wrongly classified records.

the best category in table 5, as it fluctuates between 58 and 100 percent, with most categories having a precision greater than 80 percent and all except one greater than 75 percent.¹² The coverage of all categories is estimated to be between 57 and 89 percent. All categories mostly include the correct editions and cover most of the relevant records.

Table 5: Evaluation results of the main categories

Main category	Precision (plausible)	Precision (good)	Precision (best)	Coverage
Education	0.96	0.87	0.83	0.64
Ephemera-entertainment	0.97	0.93	0.87	0.89
Ephemera-practical	0.96	0.91	0.86	0.71
History	0.88	0.67	0.58	0.65
Law	0.93	0.82	0.78	0.89
Literature and arts	0.96	0.8	0.78	0.86
Philosophy	1	1	1	0.81
Politics	0.94	0.8	0.77	0.57
Religion	0.95	0.89	0.82	0.89
Science	1	0.88	0.88	0.76

In some categories, most or all “errors” are in fact ambiguities, as the majority are erased by extending the definition of correct category from “the best one possible” to “plausible.” This is also true at an aggregate level: 81 percent of the editions in the sample obtained the best possible score, whereas 95 percent were at least plausible (see table 6 for more details). This means that almost a fifth of the assigned categories were at least somewhat contested by at least one annotator, but more than two-thirds of these contested labels were still considered to be reasonable (plausible) even if not ideal. These 0.5-point divergences often reflect the two annotators’ slightly different views on whether a category label could be considered the best-fitting (and thus receive a score of 1) or whether they regarded another category as even more suitable, therefore assigning a 0.5. Overall, both annotators were of the opinion that this in-between score was a valuable addition to the scoring system, enabling a more finely grained evaluation of the precision of a category and accounting for the complexity of genre in the early modern period.

12. Philosophy, the most precise category, and history, the least precise one, are also very small categories in the sample and in the population they approximate (figure 5), making it possible that they are affected by the “curse of the small N” (i.e. their extremity is related to the small number of observations). However, the error analyses of the next section demonstrate that lack of precision in the history category likely relates to real problems in defining the boundaries of that category.

The conceptualisation of a single main category as being “right” was intended as a simplification that consciously ignores many of the complexities of early modern books. Nevertheless, we implemented tentative analyses on how often the notion of a single best-fitting category “failed.” This helped us to understand how much information was lost with the simplification and how much working within its confines affected our calculations. By counting instances where the annotators had commented that an edition had multiple good choices for labels as well as other disagreements about the best label (1-0.5, 1-0 score pairs from the annotators), we found 74 editions out of 1,000 that could be assigned with equal plausibility to several main categories. Some 29 of the 500 editions from the sample without labels received different main categories from the two annotators. This is roughly 6 percent of the sample and is possibly somewhat inflated by the fact that the annotators discussed divergences less frequently compared to the other sample. Both measures probably also miss some editions that are problematic for a single-category schema, but the proportion would need to rise considerably from the current 6–7 percent in order to threaten the assumption that a single main category works well enough to be a useful way to think about and compute genre.¹³

Lastly, we probed the consistency of annotator agreement. Cohen’s Kappa scores (table 6) indicate that the annotators’ assessments tend to agree to a clearly non-random degree. The score is well-known for being difficult to interpret. Yet even if strict guidelines are used (McHugh 2012), the score for quality assessment indicates strong agreement, with the confidence interval extending to moderate agreement, while the confidence interval for agreement on assigned labels is wholly within the range of nearly perfect agreement. An imbalance in quality labels (both annotators gave a score of 1 in more than 80 percent of instances) might explain why the evaluation sample received a lower Kappa score (even at random, most quality annotations would have matched). Based on the raw match rate of annotations, the annotators agree on 95 percent of the quality assessments of the labels (table 4). The agreement on assigned labels is 94 percent by this measure. We conclude that the annotators’ assessments of what is the right label converge to a very high degree, suggesting that the conceptualisation of genre works well in most instances.

13. For example, averaging the number of editions belonging to different genres when the two annotators disagreed is a concession to the fact that the conceptualisation of a single main category per edition was not always applicable when doing calculations.

Table 6: Annotator agreement (Aa) and label quality estimated; 95 percent confidence intervals

Sample	Measure	2.5% bound	Estimate	97.5% bound	N
Sample with genre labels	Cohen's Kappa (Aa)	0.78	0.82	0.87	996
Sample without genre labels	Cohen's Kappa (Aa)	0.91	0.93	0.96	500
Sample with genre labels	Prob. of agreement (Aa)	0.94	0.95	0.96	996
Sample without genre labels	Prob. of agreement (Aa)	0.92	0.94	0.96	500
Sample with genre labels	Best labels	0.79	0.81	0.83	996
Sample with genre labels	Good labels	0.83	0.86	0.88	996
Sample with genre labels	Plausible labels	0.94	0.95	0.96	996

Cohen's Kappa was calculated with the psych R package (Revelle 2024).

5.2 Distant and close reading of correlated categories

Our aim is not to downplay the errors in the data. In fact, they are rather interesting as objects of analysis in themselves, since they demonstrate the problematic aspects of any attempted classification scheme of early modern books and pamphlets. Although the data we have about errors is not extensive (less than 200 observations “produced” information about errors in labels), a combination of distant and close reading enabled us to produce plausible explanations showing how some of the errors are related to structural overlaps that existed in early modern print culture. These overlaps also illustrate the differing literary conventions and traditions of the eighteenth century, when genres now considered distinct were combined much more frequently and loosely. As figure 2 demonstrates, the errors are very unequally distributed. Some pairs of real and assigned categories barely exist in the evaluated sample, but others are very significant. Notably, tens of percent of documents best classified as politics end up in law. In figure 2, history “bleeds” into politics, literature and arts, and religion to a considerable degree given the small size of the category¹⁴, while figure 3 illustrates how history mistakenly includes editions better classified as literature, politics, education or science. In contrast, categories related to formalised and well-established discourses like law and religion are more resistant to losing a significant proportion of their records to other categories.

14. See for example figure 5.

Figure 2: Errors (label did not qualify as “good”) in the evaluated sample compared to the estimated size (no. of “good” labels) of the real category

Figure 3: Errors (label did not qualify as “good”) in the evaluated sample compared to the estimated size (no. of “good” labels) of the assigned category

The results of the quantitative error analysis prompted us to take additional steps, such as creating supercategories that combine multiple main categories. Our reasoning was that, in some instances, it is better to treat highly correlated

categories (especially politics and law) as one category. What these supercategories lose in granularity, they gain in robustness. The second step was to examine some of the problematic categories more closely. Our conclusion is that categorisation problems largely reflect problems in applying clear-cut modern categories to early modern books; however, they also provide tentative directions for further research on classifying the genre and topic of ESTC records.

In the close reading, we focused in particular on the connection between law and politics, the overlap between religion and politics, and the issue of history, the least precise category. The connection between politics and law is rather straightforward: politics as a category often deals with the law and is distinguished less by substance than by register or rhetoric. The following is the title of a record (T52822) from our sample that was classified as law:

The worth of liberty consider'd: in a letter to a Member of the House of Commons upon the question, how far the late act against the immoderate use of spiritous liquors may affect the properties of all the people.

Both researchers gave this label a score of 0.5, as the document's content is an argumentative discourse about legislation rather than primary legislation as such. However, it certainly relates to legislation. This thematic overlap does not mean that the difference between the two categories would somehow be arbitrary: it is plausible that the argumentative language of early modern politics (or even its description, such as the one given in the title) could be distinguished from language strictly confined to legislative issues as such. For making such distinctions, state-of-the-art tools in machine learning or computational linguistics could be useful.

Another common (in relative terms) overlap occurs between religion and politics, which shows the complexity of applying modern genre categories to historical periods. In the early modern period, religion and politics were much more intertwined than is the case today. Sermons in particular were often very topical, especially during the English Civil War, and could touch on important political issues of the day. Debates about the rights of religious minorities—such as Dissenters (Protestants who were not members of the established Church of England) and Jews—contained a combination of religious and political arguments. These prevalent overlaps led the annotators to reflect on and discuss how to deal with cases where the outward form suggests one genre (here: religion) and the topic, as indicated by the title, is either a mix of at least two genres (here: politics and religion) or leans more towards a genre that is different to the form (here: politics).

Below is a record (T202404) from our sample with the assigned category of religion, illustrating the overlap between religion and politics and the difficulty

of evaluating which of the two genres is the most fitting description for such works.

The young cobbler of Gloucester: or, Magna Charta [sic] discours'd of between a poor man and his wife. As also several high-church principles discussed, ... Together, with reflections upon several of the vices of the high-church clergy, by the cobbler and his wife.

One of the annotators assigned a score of 1 on the basis that the subtitle “reflections upon several of the vices of the high-church clergy” indicates that the work is primarily religious in nature, and thus the most fitting genre label. The other annotator agreed that religion was a plausible genre, but thought the work was even more likely to have a political thrust, as evidenced by the title’s references to Magna Carta and High Church principles (which often went hand in hand with support for the Tory party). Here, the annotators’ motivations for assigning their respective scores are a testament to how their respective judgement is shaped by their own academic interest and domain knowledge.

The category with the lowest precision, history, provides interesting insights into how history writing was practised in the early modern period. On the face of it, a title containing phrases such as “a history of” should serve as a reasonably good predictor that the work in question belongs to the genre of history. However, during our annotation process, we discovered that works seemingly historical in nature could, in fact, sometimes be entirely fictional. Distinguishing between biographies of real and invented persons was particularly difficult, as early modern biographers tended to title their works “true” or “authentic” regardless of whether their subject ever existed, and fiction writers frequently mimicked the writing style and conventions of nonfiction genres (e.g. ESTC records T110215 and T173534). An additional challenge was in deciding on the cut-off point at which a work is considered historical. In the early modern period, many historiographers wrote works covering events up to the present, often with a view to intervening in contemporaneous political debates. Deciding whether a work describing recent events, such as a war that happened 20 years earlier, belonged to the genre of history or politics was not always straightforward, especially since the title itself often gives little insight into whether the work is primarily focused on describing the past or on using the past for present-day politics. One example of this overlap is record N9975 below:

M[emoirs and observations] of the occurrences of Europe, Since the treaties of Nimeguen and Ryswick, with relation to the present treaty at Utrecht. Shewing, that it is of the last importance that England have a footing upon the continent.

This was initially labelled as history, but both annotators gave a score of 0.5 and suggested that politics was more fitting. The period covered by the work, as indicated by the title, is 1678 (Treaty of Nijmegen) to 1712, the year of publication. When the work was published, negotiations for the Treaty of Utrecht were still ongoing and the subtitle clearly indicates the author's contemporaneous political concerns.

The dividing line between religion and history—rather distinct categories in the twenty-first century—was also much more blurred in the early modern period. Biblical criticism as an academic subfield was still in its infancy, and writers of religious history freely mixed real events occurring in biblical times (e.g. the siege of Jerusalem in 70 CE) with events and figures only described in the Bible and for which historical veracity cannot be established (e.g. ESTC record W21041). Assigning such works to either history or religion was a judgement call for the annotators, since it was difficult to estimate the balance between primarily religious elements and primarily historical elements without consulting the work in question. These complexities explain why the precision rate for history is significantly lower than for all other categories. We sought to mitigate difficulties of assigning a genre in multiple ways, for example by discussing particularly complex cases, assigning a score of 0.5, and looking at a small number of original texts to see if a general rule for annotating such cases could be determined.

6 Patterns and biases of genres in the ESTC and ECCO

The new genre data introduced in this paper significantly extends the possibilities of using the ESTC and its subsets for quantitative analyses of early modern history. As established in section 2, the ESTC (alongside its subsets) has been the primary resource in attempts to chart the topic or genre composition of publishing outputs in early modern Britain. For the eighteenth century, which covers most of the editions in the ESTC, such work has only been possible for subsets or samples of the whole catalogue until now. Furthermore, there has been no framework that would have placed the entire catalogue—spanning more than 300 years—within the confines of a single concise and comprehensive classification scheme. Our categorisation covers 94 percent of all records in the ESTC. To the best of our knowledge, figure 4 is the most comprehensive depiction of the composition of early modern book publishing in the English-speaking world yet produced.

Our initial examination of figure 4 adds significant support to previous claims made about large-scale book publication trends and highlights unexpected developments that should be studied in more detail in future research. We can see the same relative decline of religion and rise of literature during the

eighteenth century as noted by earlier and more limited quantitative studies (Suarez 2009; Tolonen et al. 2021). Our results make it increasingly likely that these developments are robust and are not confined to particulars of any specific classification scheme or subset of ESTC editions analysed.

One development that warrants closer scrutiny is the rise in the proportion of political works during the decade of the English Civil War (1640s). Even after the end of the war, the proportion of political works does not return to the pre-war level. Since the relationship between the English Civil War and the emergence of a “public sphere” of political discourse in England has been discussed in qualitative research (Zaret 2000), this finding is potentially valuable if it can be regarded as reasonably accurate.¹⁵ However, since the English Civil War decade is also a threshold that separates different segments of the ESTC (consisting of several preceding catalogues), data transitions happening in the 1640s should be analysed with special care, as they can also be linked to different biases and classification conventions of the different segments (Tiihonen 2020).

Figure 4: Main categories of editions in the ESTC 1500–1800

Our categorisation may also be useful for studies focusing primarily on other datasets. The ESTC is the default resource used to examine topic or genre-related biases in other collections of early modern books, such as ECCO (Tolonen,

15. The fact that politics was a major topic in the publications of the 1640s is in itself an extremely well-known phenomenon that has been extensively studied (Raymond 2003). However, here we can compare the decade of the English Civil War to roughly 150 years both before and after it at the scale of the entire ESTC.

Mäkelä, and Lahti 2022) or the early modern section of the HathiTrust Digital Library (Almelhem et al. 2023). For researchers working with other datasets, a more comprehensive classification of the ESTC renders it a more accurate comparison point in terms of genre and topic composition, and can thus help to reveal biases in the dataset being studied.

In figure 5, we compare the category composition of the ESTC to that of ECCO, the most comprehensive full-text collection of books printed in eighteenth-century Britain. As the figure demonstrates, the collection is not an accurate representation of all the surviving editions in the ESTC. Law texts and practical ephemera are underrepresented, whereas science, history and philosophy are overrepresented to a considerable degree. This comparison extends earlier quantitative work on the biases present in ECCO (Tolonen, Mäkelä, and Lahti 2022) that could not utilise a fully classified ESTC. We can now argue more confidently that ECCO is especially skewed towards texts related to Enlightenment categories—such as philosophy and science—and that it has a tendency to exclude administrative and practical documents even though they account for a significant proportion of early modern publications.

Figure 5: Relative “bias” of ECCO compared to the ESTC by main category

7 Conclusion

Even more important than the immediate findings are the yet-unexplored possibilities offered by the new data, as well as the lessons learned from the

classification process. Together, our workflow development and evaluation process demonstrate that a good understanding of the data can create a simple, eclectic and transparent workflow that produces relevant results even for a complex historical dataset like the ESTC.¹⁶ A systematic but hands-on and humanities-oriented process of evaluating the results helped us to pinpoint the degree to which the data enrichment workflow was effective: manual evaluation allowed us not only to decide whether a category was ontologically correct, but also to consider the plausibility of any assigned category, which ended up being a very fruitful means of dealing with the various topical and thematic convolutions of early modern texts.

Our evaluation revealed that, in the ESTC, certain document types (e.g. politics and law) might benefit from a more complex classifier that leverages techniques from machine learning and computational linguistics, since keywords and titles can miss the essential elements relevant for classification. Despite the limitations discussed earlier, unsupervised and semi-supervised methods might have their use in discovering “genres” that are characterised by a complex configuration of linguistic, topical or even visual cues.¹⁷ Thus, our results highlight the necessity for projects that study early modern genres and related questions from various angles. New techniques like multimodal learning might help to derive more holistic computational interpretations of genre in the early modern period, but as we demonstrate, classification workflows can also be driven mostly by domain expertise in (for example) the bibliographic material.

The process described here will be updated. Since it is already in use in various COMHIS research projects, it is reasonable to wait for some time (e.g. a year) to see if any suggestions for improvements emerge from experiences accumulated in real-life research. We can already name a few changes and expansions that could be implemented. In a multi-step workflow with many shifting parts, there are always individual elements like specific keywords which, in hindsight, could have been added or removed.¹⁸ Larger or more targeted evaluation samples could help us learn more about the size and nature of category overlaps. One step to be taken in the near future is to enrich the pre-1700 ESTC with the keyword information from the Universal Short Title Catalogue (USTC). This

16. In the sense that various sources of information are used and the option deemed to be the best is used for classification.

17. For example, satirical illustrations may be a distinguishing feature between law and politics in early modern publications (for the political role of images, see e.g. Pierce 2008). To identify at scale which kind of images commonly appeared in which genres, it may be possible to build on a currently ongoing research strand in COMHIS, which uses deep learning algorithms to detect and classify visual elements in eighteenth-century books (Wang et al., forthcoming; for an introduction to this methodology, see Wang 2023).

18. For example, author one accepted the keyword “pirates” to map to the category literature, but no longer agrees with his previous reasoning, as it could also easily be related to political discussion too.

should significantly extend the coverage of records with a label before the eighteenth century. Another potential step is to create a version of the data in which multiple categories can exist for any given document. This would not be technically difficult to implement and, as our evaluation results demonstrate, category ambiguity was an important characteristic of early modern books published in the Anglosphere, making a strong case for a multi-label version. The data could also benefit from a formal approach to modelling genres. Scope notes for genres could improve rigour and cross-disciplinary communication, and an explicitly hierarchical genre model could be implemented for additional technical clarity. Combined with formal identifiers for the genres, this could make the data introduced in this article more compatible with Linked Open Data (LOD) standards. In the best-case scenario, genre data could be linked with other historical datasets in the future.

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Appendices

Appendix A—Supplementary data

Table 7: Full list of subcategories

Act	Adventure	Advertisement	Advice	Aesthetics
Agriculture	Almanac	Ancient history	Antiquarianism	Applied knowledge
Architecture	Astrology	Astronomy	Bible	Bill
Biography	Calendar	Catalogue	Catechism	Chemistry
Classics	Comedy	Commerce	Conduct of life	Cooking
Declaration	Devotional exercise	Dictionary	Doctrine	Fable

For children	Geography and nature	Handbook	Hobbies and games	Human mind
Hymn	Language	Linguistics	Logic	Manners
Mathematics	Medicine	Memoir	Metaphysics	Meteorology
Military applications	Moral	Music	Navigation	News
Novel	Opera	Painting	Pastoral letter	Periodical
Petition	Physics	Play	Poem	Political thought
Prayer book	Proceeding	Proclamation	Psalm	Report
Review	Satire	Satire poem	Sermon	Song
Speech	Technology	Theatre programme	Theoretical	Theory of knowledge
Travel	Trial	Utopia		

Appendix B—Technical details

Prominence score F of a main category for an edition \mathbf{x} and main category \mathbf{c} was calculated in the following way:

$$F(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{x}) = \sum_{k \in (K_{\mathbf{x}} \cap K_{\mathbf{c}})} \ln(Q(k))$$

Where \mathbf{k} is a keyword or title n -gram in the ESTC, $K_{\mathbf{x}}$ is the set of keywords or title n -grams related to the edition \mathbf{x} , and $K_{\mathbf{c}}$ is the set of keywords or title n -grams related to main category \mathbf{c} . Function Q measures the number of times that the keyword or n -gram appears in the ESTC. In verbal form: the prominence score is a sum of natural logarithms of the prominences of keywords or n -grams that relate to an edition and one main category. Constructed in this manner, the equation favours the information provided by the most common keywords and title n -grams. The main category of the edition was chosen by picking the category \mathbf{c} with the highest prominence score.

Appendix C—Exploratory statistical approaches

The primary explorative method used to find relevant keywords and n -grams for the classification workflow was to computationally detect those that were heavily associated with a main category in an already labelled subset of the data, and then analyse these keywords and n -grams manually to ascertain whether they had a direct and meaningful relation to that main category. If the connection between the keyword or n -gram and the main category was deemed plausible enough, it was typically included in the labelling process.

The first author still reserved the right to make any substance-based edits, for example by assigning the connection between an n-gram and main category wholly by hand or by adding n-grams or keywords that did not emerge through this process to the workflow.

In practice, this was implemented by analysing how often a keyword or n-gram manifested in a given main category (e.g. whether more than half of its appearances were concentrated in one main category). Another important measure was how disproportionately a keyword or n-gram manifested in a specific category compared to what we would have expected, if the topic or n-gram was equally distributed between different main categories. Since it was possible to implement these comparisons to all of the n-grams and topics analysed at once (combined with other filtering choices like how common the keyword or n-gram was in the data), it enabled the first author to restrict manual evaluation work to those keywords and n-grams that had at least a substantial correlational relationship to some main category, and hence a much greater likelihood of being useful for classification. This process required pre-labelled data to infer n-grams and topics with “overrepresentation” in a main category. In our case, such data was initially provided via manually labelled data. It became possible to repeat this investigation of correlations between topics and n-grams and main categories with a larger dataset when the data grew. The replication package of this article includes a script and an output table—similar to the tables that were then checked manually to select keywords and n-grams for the workflow—that demonstrate this approach.

This process is an example of utilising noisy correlations to find—rather than confirm—connections between main categories and n-grams/topics that have a meaningful interpretation. Manual confirmation of the included n-grams and topics was very important, as the reasons for specific correlations were occasionally very misleading, and it would have been questionable to project them to further classification. For example, the n-gram “our lord” was heavily overrepresented in the category ephemera-practical. This is understandable, as it is a jargon-like expression in the full title of early modern almanacs (“published in the year of our lord X”). But “our lord” has no substantial correlation to this main category. As it has a substantial correlation to categories like religion and politics, it is possible that mapping the bigram to ephemera-practical would lead to many out-of-sample documents in those categories being labelled as ephemera-practical.

This example highlights the more general motivations of our method. Given the high-dimensional and heterogeneous nature of our data, correlations as such are heavily influenced by random chance and the particulars of the specific subset of data used to detect them, making projections unreliable. As the possible explanations for correlations vastly outnumber those that tie a keyword or n-gram to a meaningful relationship with a main category, the

default approach was to require a historically grounded and robust explanation for a topic or keyword to be included. This does not mean that the keywords and n-grams included in the workflow are wholly unproblematic (we are not aware of such instances), but as we hope to demonstrate, sometimes correlation reflects genuine connections between the units of information that we use and genres as we conceptualise them.

An example of an included n-gram would be the bigram “performed at,” which had a heavy statistical association with the category “arts.” This expression was frequently used in the titles of plays (belonging to the category of arts¹⁹) published in London, and we are not aware of any serious convolutions that could lead to other publication types using this expression consistently. Still, there was an element of concession in including expressions like this in the workflow, as the connection between the bigram and the main category to which it maps is of a second-degree nature. A publication could address something being performed without necessarily being a publication that best belongs in the category arts, but to the best of our understanding, the expression was mostly used in the context of plays.

An even stronger example of an included n-gram is the bigram “a sermon.” Sermons were an established text type in eighteenth-century Britain, and thousands of publications define themselves as such in their title. Even this bigram is not wholly unproblematic, as there are individual instances of political or philosophical essays and commentaries whose titles contain phrases like “in a response to a sermon preached at.” Still, having “a sermon” in the title is an almost ideal piece of information for the workflow, as it maps directly to the classification scheme (sermons are assigned to the category “religion” by default).

19. In the first four steps of the workflow, arts and literature are still treated as separate categories, after which they are merged together.